

<https://www.iprolepsis.eu>

PROLEPSIS

HorizonEurope-funded project developing a novel personalised digital care ecosystem for people with PsA

iPROLEPSIS project newsletter | Issue No. 2

September 2023

Welcome! This is the second edition of the Newsletter series of the iPROLEPSIS project. In this newsletter issue, we delve into the transformative power of user research and co-creation in the healthcare innovation research process.

Inside this issue

Exploring **User Research** and Co-Creation in **Healthcare Innovation**: Putting Psoriatic Arthritis (PsA) Patients and **Healthcare Practitioners (HCPs)** First

Funded by
the European Union

iPROLEPSIS received funding from the European Union under Grant Agreement No. 101095697.

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Health and Digital Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the European Health and Digital Executive Agency can be held responsible for them.

<https://www.iprolepsis.eu>

The iPROLEPSIS Digital Health Ecosystem

Within the iPROLEPSIS, we aim to develop a suite of **digital health tools (DHTs)** designed to **detect early transitions to PsA, predict flares** for timely intervention, and **provide personalised recommendations and interventions** for managing the disease.

The DHTs to be developed:

miPROLEPSIS
patient app

biAURA biaural
sounds app

miPROLEPSIS HCPs
dashboard

Personalised Gaming
Suite (PGS)

Personalised
recommendation system

PROLEPSIS DHTs development follows an **iterative User Research & Co-Creation approach**. It started in August 2023 with initial technical specifications, architecture, and product backlog development, considering user research and co-creation session results for the first product version.

iPROLEPSIS Ecosystem Roadmap

<https://www.iprolepsis.eu>

User Research and Co-creation

Our innovative approach blends **Lean, Scrum, and Design Thinking methodologies**, placing social innovation and patient-centered perspectives at the core.

By engaging **PsA patients, clinicians, and healthcare enablers** in agile co-creation, we aim to **map user needs, guide research questions, develop empathy/journey maps, and identify core user stories**, laying the foundation for the iPROLEPSIS digital health ecosystem.

The End-users engagement strategy involves:

User research focus groups

Online surveys

Continuous co-creation workshops

iPROLEPSIS user research procedure

<https://www.iprolepsis.eu>

Focus Groups and Survey

Focus groups

The **iPROLEPSIS focus groups**, an increasingly popular method in health research, aimed to gather patient insights on disease activity, management, care needs, and their attitudes toward digital biomarkers for future development directions.

The **iPROLEPSIS** team between January and May 2023:

Conducted

10

Focus groups

Spoken with

39

PsA patients

From

Countries

4 Themes emerged from the focus group discussions:

Disease activity

Coping

Care Experience

Digital Biomarkers

Survey

A comprehensive **survey** was designed to obtain more specific input from a broader range of PsA patients. The **survey covered** various aspects, dedicated to:

Demographics & Technological experience

miPROLEPSIS patient app - Content & Appearance

BiAURA app - preferences

Personalised SeriousGaming Suite - Content and Appearance

The aim was to collect responses from 100 patients per country. Based on the provided data, the demographics of technological literacy and device usage across different countries were analysed.

Key Takeaways

Key takeaways from User research and Co-creation:

Complexity

The iPROLEPSIS aims to develop DHTs for a complex healthcare context. **The compatibility of these innovations with diverse care systems is crucial** for successful adoption.

Heterogeneity

PsA is highly diverse, presenting varying symptoms, severity, and onset ages. **Designing DHTs for such diversity is challenging.**

Trial and Error

PsA patients navigate uncertainty **through trial and error**. **iPROLEPSIS DHTs aim to support them in this process.**

Preference Differences

Survey and focus groups revealed diverse DHTs preferences. Clarity in explanations, visuals, colours, notifications, and daily questions are crucial.

Insights from patients with PsA:

“Digital health platforms have the potential to be very useful, but it is also important to ensure the quality of the information available. I have tried a few platforms related to my condition, and my experience has been mixed. Some have been very helpful, with features such as symptom tracking, disease education and a supportive community. However, others have been less reliable and have not provided relevant or accurate information.”

“I would like to see information about daily symptoms, such as pain, joint stiffness and fatigue. It would also be useful to have a record of daily activities, such as exercise and sleep quality.”

“It would also help a lot to understand the evolution of the disease, and what could also cause a crisis, because there are situations that sometimes trigger a crisis, and it would also help us, the patients, to understand what we could change, what we could do, to minimize the pain, and also the doctor to have a record of these situations.”

What's next?

In the upcoming phase, we will involve co-creation with patient partners, focusing on design sprints to develop the miPROLEPSIS PDPID app. This version is set to launch in December 2023.